

Revisiting natural and laboratory electron spin resonance (ESR) dose response curves of quartz from Chinese loess

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Abstract

Natural and laboratory ESR dose response curves (DRCs) of $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}]^0$ and $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ were investigated for samples of quartz from the Luochuan loess-palaeosol master section, Chinese Loess Plateau. The natural and laboratory DRCs show a clear divergence above ~ 1000 Gy, with much lower D_0 values and saturation levels observed for the natural DRCs, which is in agreement with the previous study by Tsukamoto et al. (2018). Young (< 15 ka) samples from Luochuan and Jingbian – another site of the Chinese Loess Plateau, together with two modern samples of Chinese loess, were used to investigate the residual signals of $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}]^0$ and $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ centres. Our results are in line with published studies and show that the significant residual signals corresponding to several tens to hundreds of Gy are present in both Al and Ti centres. These need to be taken into account before laboratory DRC construction. ESR pulse annealing experiments performed on samples irradiated with different doses show an apparent dose-dependent thermal instability of $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}]^0$ and $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$, with the signals for higher doses decaying faster with increasing temperature. We attribute the change in D_0 with preheat reported in Tsukamoto et al., 2018, as well as the difference between laboratory and natural DRCs, to this apparent dose-dependent thermal instability of the signals. The saturation level of the natural DRC, being the result of reaching the equilibrium between filling of the traps and emptying them due to thermal decay, is therefore additionally affected at higher doses, due to the increased thermal instability. The inability to recreate in the laboratory the same response to irradiation as the one observed in nature questions the accuracy of dating samples beyond ~ 1000 Gy.

Keywords: Electron spin resonance (ESR); quartz; loess; Luochuan; dose response curve

1. Introduction

Recreating a response of a crystalline material to natural radiation by means of artificial irradiation in laboratory is one of the basic assumptions of trapped charge dating methods. While numerous applications of electron spin resonance (ESR) and luminescence techniques in geochronology (e.g. Duval et al., 2017; Murray et al., 2008, 2021; Watanuki et al., 2005) have shown, by comparing the results with independent ages, that this assumption holds true, many studies (e.g. Avram et al., 2020; Chapot et al., 2012; Timar-Gabor & Wintle, 2013; Tsukamoto et al., 2018) have also demonstrated that the relationship between natural and laboratory DRCs requires closer examination. Very low dose rates observed in nature make it impossible to directly measure how the natural signal is accumulating over time. Recreating the growth of the natural signal is possible by measuring the natural signal from samples with a known age (and consequently a known natural dose because the dose rate can be measured) and coming from the same site so that there is no sample-to-sample variability in luminescence or ESR characteristics. By plotting the natural luminescence/ESR signals as a function of the calculated absorbed dose a natural dose response curve (DRC) can be constructed. This curve can then be compared with a laboratory DRC, to examine the validity of this assumption. However, finding a site with a well-established independent chronology over a wide age range and containing homogeneous materials suitable for ESR or luminescence dating is a challenge.

Fortunately, the Chinese Loess Plateau provides such an opportunity. It represents an almost continuous and complete record of terrestrial sedimentation for the past 2.6 Ma, thus covering the late Pliocene up until the Holocene (Ding et al., 1998; Sun et al., 1998). A general stratigraphical framework across the Central Loess Plateau has been accepted based on correlations between magnetic susceptibility curves, marine isotope records and identified geomagnetic polarity reversals (Heller and Liu, 1986; Kukla et al., 1988; Kukla and An, 1989).

Quartz from the Chinese Loess Plateau has been used for comparing the natural and laboratory DRCs by Chapot et al., (2012, 2016) in luminescence studies (optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) and thermally transferred optically stimulated luminescence (TT-OSL), respectively), and later by Tsukamoto et al. (2018) in ESR studies. Their results were alarming, as the natural and laboratory curves did not overlap above certain doses, and the natural DRC was characterised by a much lower saturation dose (D_0) and saturation level. For TT-OSL and ESR signals, thermal instability was proposed as the cause of this divergence.

However, there have been no subsequent studies aiming at understanding the underlying mechanisms, and, which is perhaps even more pressing, trying to address the implications of these findings for the ESR and luminescence dating community. The inability to recreate the same response to irradiation observed in nature by artificial means, which was demonstrated for higher doses, throws into question the accuracy of dating samples beyond the point of this divergence. This becomes especially relevant in attempts to assess the dating range of ESR and luminescence techniques. Additionally, Tsukamoto et al. (2018) showed that the D_0 values of the laboratory curves depend on the preheat temperature applied, decreasing with the temperature, which provokes more questions about the validity of preheating. This calls for an in-depth investigation of the underlying mechanisms. With that in mind, in this work we revisit the natural and laboratory ESR dose response curves of $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}]^0$ (subsequently called Al-h centre) and $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ (where M^+ can be either Li^+ , H^+ or Na^+ ; subsequently called Ti centres) from Chinese loess, by analysing quartz from the Luochuan loess-palaeosol master section. Young (<15 ka) samples from Luochuan and Jingbian – another site of the Chinese Loess Plateau, together with two modern samples of Chinese loess, were used to investigate the residual signals of Al-h and Ti centres. ESR pulse annealing experiments were performed to study thermal stability of the centres. Our results show an apparent dose-dependent thermal instability, which explains the divergence between the natural and laboratory DRC, and the changes observed due to preheat.

2. Experimental

2.1 Site description and sampling

Four sets of samples collected on the Chinese Loess Plateau were investigated in this study: two sets from Luochuan (at Xiaheimu and at Potou), one from Jingbian and one set comprised of two modern samples.

The Luochuan (35°45'N, 109°25'E) loess-paleosol sequence is considered a standard pedostratigraphic section of the Chinese Loess Plateau and a key section for paleoclimate research (e.g., Bronger, 2003; Forman, 1991; Heller & Evans, 1995; Heller & Liu, 1982; Kukla & An, 1989; Porter & An, 1995). Located in the central part of the plateau in the Shaanxi province, the 135 m thick section comprises more than 30 loess-paleosol alternations (Gallet et al., 1996). Based on previous paleomagnetic stratigraphic research and biostratigraphy, the onset of loess accumulation is estimated at 2.35 Ma (Kukla and An, 1989) or ~ 2.5 Ma ago (Liu and Ding, 1998). Three samples were collected at the Xiaheimu

section and thirteen samples at the Potou section. Sample codes and the units in which they were collected are given in **Table 1**.

The loess-palaeosol sequence at Jingbian (37°499'N, 108°905'E) was first described by Ding et al. (1999) and is located at the northern edge of the Chinese Loess Plateau, close to the Mu Us desert. The S1 soil, 5-6 m thick, which can be traced laterally across multiple gullies, is covered by sandy L1 loess of the last glacial (Buylaert et al., 2015). Later, a detailed luminescence dating study carried out by Stevens et al. (2018) showed multiple hiatuses in the loess-palaeosol sequence at this location. In this study we use two young (<15 ka) samples collected in the L1 and S0 units at section D from Stevens et al.

We also use two modern/young samples from Buylaert et al., 2011. These were collected from the top few cm of apparently undisturbed loess sections in the Chinese Loess Plateau, at Zhou he zhen bei (37°07.910'N, 108°40.887'E) and at Shi mao (37°56.183'N, 109°58.930'E).

2.2 Sample processing and expected dose determination

Sample preparation for both ESR analysis and OSL determination of the equivalent dose for the natural samples were conducted at the Nordic Laboratory for Luminescence Dating (Technical University of Denmark, Risø campus) in Roskilde, Denmark. Standard laboratory preparation was followed for extracting the coarse (63–90 and 90–180 μm , see **Table 1**) quartz from the samples (see e.g., Buylaert et al., 2011, 2015; Stevens et al., 2018). Quartz OSL equivalent doses for the Jingbian samples (D381 codes) and modern/young loess (D codes) were reported in Buylaert et al. (2011) and Stevens et al. (2018), respectively.

For the A881 samples and sample D88102, quartz OSL measurements were performed using Risø TL/OSL-DA-20 readers (Thomsen et al., 2008) to determine the equivalent doses. Stimulation was performed by blue light emitting diodes (470 ± 30 nm). For measurement purposes the quartz grains were mounted as large (8 mm aliquots) on stainless steel disks using silicone oil as adhesive. The equivalent dose for the coarse (63–90 μm) quartz fraction was obtained by employing a SAR protocol (Murray and Wintle, 2003, 2000) (Murray & Wintle, 2000, 2003) using a preheat/cut-heat setting of 220°C for 10s and 180°C with immediate cooling. Net OSL signals were calculated using early background subtraction (first 0.8 s minus the following 0.8s of the decay curve) and DRCs were fitted using single saturation exponential functions in the *Analyst v4.57* software package.

The equivalent doses for the samples from Potou (see **Table 1**) were estimated based on

ages reported in Ding et al., 2002. First, the expected age for each sample was determined by taking the median age of two nearest palaeosol/loess transitions from the Chiloparts record. Expected equivalent doses were then determined by multiplying the expected age of the sample by the average dose rate of ~ 3 Gy/ka (Chapot et al., 2012).

The equivalent doses obtained from OSL measurements, and estimated based on data from Ding et al. (2002), are further referred to as expected doses, to differentiate them from the equivalent doses calculated as a result of constructing DRCs from ESR intensities.

2.3 ESR measurements

ESR measurements were performed on an X band Bruker EMX Plus Spectrometer at the Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania. All samples were placed in quartz glass tubes filled with a mass of 200 ± 10 mg by maintaining the same volume. All ESR measurements were normalized to 100 mg for inter-comparison. Each sample was measured 3-8 times and rotated in the cavity between the measurements. A mean ESR intensity was used for D_E calculation, and standard error was indicated in all the plots. Exposure of samples to sunlight during measurements was restricted to a minimum. Measurements were carried out at 90 K (in liquid nitrogen) for Al-h and Ti centres. Al-h spectra were acquired using the following settings: 3350 ± 150 G scanned magnetic field, modulation amplitude 1 G, modulation frequency 100 kHz, microwave power 2 mW, conversion time 40 ms, time constant 40 ms. The intensity of Al-h signal was evaluated from peak-to-peak amplitude measurements between the top of the first peak ($g = 2.018$) to the bottom of the last peak ($g = 1.993$) (Toyoda and Falguères, 2003)(**Fig. S1a**). For Ti measurements the settings were: 3490 ± 110 G scanned magnetic field, modulation amplitude 1 G, modulation frequency 100 kHz, microwave power 10.02 mW, conversion time 10 ms, time constant 20.48 ms, and 10-20 scans per measurement. Most of the Ti spectra required a baseline correction, which was performed using Bruker's Xenon software. The intensities of the Ti centre signals were obtained following Duval & Guilarte, 2015 and Duval et al., 2017, using "options A, B and D", as referred to therein, associated with a mixture of Ti-H and Ti-Li centers. Option A was measured from the top of $g = 1.979$ to the bottom of the peak around $g = 1.913$ - 1.915 , option B as a peak-to-peak amplitude of the signal at $g = 1.931$ and option D as a peak-to-baseline amplitude of the signal $g = 1.913$ - 1.915 (**Fig. S1b**).

Gamma irradiations were performed at room temperature at the Department of Health Technology at DTU (Dosimetry Research Unit) using a calibrated ^{60}Co gamma cell with a dose rate of 1.882 ± 0.041 Gy/s.

Pulse annealing ESR experiments were carried out by heating a single aliquot of each of four selected samples in the oven for 10 min, over a temperature range 295-895 K, with 50 K steps. Since in the pulse annealing experiment the dependence between temperature and time is linear, it can be written as $T = T_0 + Qt$, where T_0 is the room temperature (~ 295 K), t is time, and Q is the heating rate, which can be expressed as $Q = q/t_a$, where t_a is the annealing duration (600 s) and q is the temperature increment from pulse to pulse (50 K) (Benzid and Timar Gabor, 2020).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Residual signals

The issue of bleachability of Al-h centre has been addressed in several studies, e.g., Duval et al., 2017; Timar-Gabor et al., 2020; Tissoux et al., 2007; Toyoda et al., 2000; Tsukamoto et al., 2017, 2018; Voinchet et al., 2003; based on these studies it is generally accepted that sunlight exposure does not completely bleach the ESR intensity, and the signal is reset only to a non-bleachable residual level. Tsukamoto et al. (2018) derived the Al-h natural DRC for Chinese loess samples from Luochuan and observed the x-intercept of ~ 500 Gy, likely due to the residual signal resulting from incomplete bleaching. Timar-Gabor et al. (2020) reported similar residual dose values of the Al-h centre by analysing young sedimentary quartz of known OSL ages.

In contrast to the Al-h centre, the Ti centre is known to be fully bleachable and is completely bleached after a few hundred hours of solar simulator bleaching (Tissoux et al., 2007; Toyoda et al., 2000). Therefore, residual subtraction has not been considered in the initial studies of the Ti centre. However, Tsukamoto et al. (2017) observed residual doses in modern aeolian sediments ranging from 61 ± 2 Gy to as much as 466 ± 25 Gy (excluding the largest value gave an average of 94 ± 20 Gy). Similarly, Richter et al. (2020) observed an overestimation of the equivalent doses of the youngest samples from Luochuan which gave a residual dose of ~ 100 Gy (~ 30 ka), suggesting that it could be caused by the incomplete resetting of the Ti signal. In Tsukamoto et al., 2018 a non-zero x-intercept of the Ti natural DRC can be noticed (Fig. 3 therein), indicating the existence of the residual signal in loess samples from Luochuan. Timar-Gabor et al. (2020) reported residual doses in aeolian sand

ranging from 98 ± 11 Gy to 209 ± 236 Gy, and as much as 575 ± 44 Gy for quartz from Holocene loess soil from Roxolany, Ukraine. All these data suggest that determining the residual signal and subtracting its intensity from the total intensity before construction the DRC should be performed for both the Ti centres and the Al-h centre.

To investigate the residual signals, we measured the signals of Al-h and Ti centres in modern and young (expected dose below 60 Gy) samples from Luochuan, Jingbian, Zhou he zhen bei and Shi mao (**Fig. 1**). Including different sampling sites in this analysis ensured that the observed phenomenon is not site-specific.

Fig. 1a shows residual amplitudes observed for Al-h centre. The values for Luochuan and Jingbian samples were quite consistent, while the modern samples exhibited slightly higher values which we attribute to the fact that these modern samples have not yet undergone their full transport – deposition cycle and tend to underestimate the degree of bleaching (Jain et al., 2004). Taking into account only the samples from Luochuan (D881 01, 02 and A881 01, 25, 34), the average residual intensity was calculated to be 1.136 ± 0.006 , which is equal to as much as 75% of the amplitude registered for 960 Gy of expected dose.

The intensities of the Ti signals for young samples from Luochuan are shown in **Fig. 1b**. Ti centre in the modern samples and the samples from Jingbian were below the detection level. It is worth pointing out here that Ti signals for the young samples were extremely weak, often close to the noise level, and measuring their amplitudes was possible only after careful baseline correction and comparing the peak positions with the other, stronger spectra. Consequently, the obtained amplitudes carry additional uncertainties, not reflected in the standard error (as it takes into account only the standard deviation between measurements and their number, and not the sensitivity of the measurement). The average Ti amplitudes for the Luochuan samples were 0.036 ± 0.002 , 0.038 ± 0.002 , 0.027 ± 0.002 , for option A, B, and D respectively, which corresponds to a much smaller than in the case of Al-h percentage of the amplitude registered for 960 Gy of expected dose, equal to about 20%.

The residual signal intensities of Al-h and Ti centres calculated for the Luochuan samples were used for correction of the natural and laboratory DRCs, by subtracting these intensities from the total intensity of each datapoint of the DRCs.

3.2 Natural and laboratory DRCs

The main issue which we would like to address in this study is the divergence between the natural and the laboratory DRCs. This divergence has previously been reported for quartz

from Luochuan loess samples, first in Chapot et al., 2012, 2016 for luminescence (OSL and TT-OSL) signals, and later in Tsukamoto et al., 2018 for ESR signals. Tsukamoto et al. (2018) performed a series of ESR experiments, where irradiated aliquots were preheated to different temperatures (no preheat, 150, 180, 20 and 240°C). In addition to lowering of the saturation level, the decrease of D_0 value with increasing preheat temperature was reported. They observed that preheat with the highest temperatures brings the laboratory DRC closer to the natural one, although the D_0 values for these preheated curves are still much larger than those obtained for the natural DRC. We obtained the natural DRCs for Al-h and Ti centres by plotting ESR intensities of the natural samples against the expected natural dose (see **Table 1**). The laboratory DRCs were created using 7 aliquots of sample D881 06 (expected dose 384 ± 38 Gy) and D881 12 (expected dose 960 ± 96 Gy) each, irradiated with different gamma doses between 0 and 8000 Gy. We applied a correction to the DRCs, by subtracting the residual signal from each datapoint's intensity. Only Luochuan samples were taken into account while calculating the residual intensity (values were given in the previous section), to eliminate the variability observed between sites (**Fig. 1**). The DRCs plotted without the correction were presented in the Supplementary material (**Fig. S2**)

Curves were fitted using a single saturating exponential function

$$I(D) = I_0(1 - e^{-(D-D_E)/D_0}) \quad (1)$$

where I is the ESR intensity, D is the laboratory dose, I_0 is the high-dose asymptote of the saturating exponential, D_E is the dose intercept; referred to as the equivalent dose, and D_0 is the saturation dose, at which a fraction $(1-e^{-1})$ of the total number of traps is filled. D_0 parameter can be interpreted as the inverse value of the probability of a population of traps being filled per unit dose. The higher the D_0 values, the higher the dose at which saturation occurs and the smaller the fraction of traps filled per unit dose.

Fig. 2a shows the corrected natural and laboratory DRCs for Al-h centre. The natural DRC for Al-h is poorly defined due to large scatter in the region between 500 and 1000 Gy, and after residual correction resembles a plateau, which made fitting with an exponential curve impossible. However, the saturating shape of the natural DRC is clearer when looking at the data uncorrected for the residual dose (**Fig. S2**), where the datapoints measured for the young samples are present. Equivalent dose (D_E) values obtained from fitting of the laboratory DRCs (**Fig. 2a** inset) were 1061 ± 103 Gy for sample D881 06 and 925 ± 181 Gy for sample D881 12 (**Table 2**). While the D_E value for the younger sample, with the expected

dose 384 ± 38 Gy, is overestimated by 176%, the value for the older one is in good agreement with the expected dose of 960 ± 96 Gy.

The corrected natural and laboratory DRCs for Ti centres are presented in **Fig. 2b, c, d**. The natural DRC for Ti centres could be fitted with a single saturating exponential function, however a significant scattering of the datapoints was observed, especially for the higher doses. D_E values obtained from fitting for sample D881 06 were 483 ± 75 Gy, 489 ± 53 Gy, 451 ± 25 Gy for options A, B, D respectively; and for sample D881 12 the values were 1421 ± 109 Gy, 1244 ± 102 Gy, 1426 ± 106 Gy, for option A, B, D, respectively (**Table 2**). In the case of Ti centers, the equivalent dose for the sample D881 06, although slightly larger, agrees within the uncertainty with the expected value of 384 ± 38 Gy, while the D_E value for the older sample is overestimated by between 30 and 49%.

Fig. 2 presents the data in two ways, using different horizontal axes. In the insets, the “traditional” representation was used, where the datapoints are plotted against the laboratory dose, which allows for a quick visual estimation of the equivalent doses – the intercept of the DRC with the x axis. The main figures use an alternative plotting, similar to the concept of the “Australian slide” method (Prescott et al., 1993). In this approach, the datapoints are plotted against the total dose – the sum of the expected and laboratory dose (in the case of natural samples the total dose is the same as the expected dose), which results in a horizontal shift, the “slide”, of laboratory DRCs by the value of the expected dose for each sample. Therefore, it can be assumed, that if the laboratory DRC is correct, when horizontally shifted by adding the expected dose values (determined by other measurements and well-established) and corrected for the residual signal (so vertically shifted down along the y axis), it should go through the origin and overlap the natural DRC (assuming that one is also correct). It is clear, that the laboratory DRCs for Al-h center for sample 06, and for Ti centres for sample 12 do not go through the origin, explaining the mismatch between the expected doses and the derived equivalent doses, which implies that there must be an issue with the measurement itself and/or the extrapolation performed in order to obtain the equivalent dose. For the Al-h centre this discrepancy might be partially explained by incomplete bleaching and the scattered nature of the natural DRC. When it comes to the incorrect shape of the extrapolation of the laboratory DRC, it is likely that the upper part of the DRC is bending the fit, resulting in the offset of the laboratory DRC for Ti. A strong correlation between the maximum irradiation dose and the final D_E value has been observed elsewhere for some materials when using the single saturation exponential function (e.g., Duval, 2012; Duval et al., 2009).

The natural and laboratory DRCs for Ti centres overlap up to 1000 Gy, and above this value they diverge significantly, with the natural DRCs saturating much faster than the laboratory one. The D_0 values for the natural DRCs obtained from the fitting were 830 ± 350 Gy, 883 ± 451 Gy, and 665 ± 336 Gy for Ti option A, B, D, respectively (**Table 2**), which are in agreement with the value of $\sim 650 \pm 110$ Gy reported in Tsukamoto et al., 2018 for the natural DRC of the Ti centre. For the Al-h centre the natural DRC is not very well-defined, however, a divergence between the natural and the laboratory curves is still clearly visible. The D_0 value can be estimated from the DRC uncorrected for the residual signal, where the datapoints for the young samples are still present (**Fig. S2**), as ranging between 500 and 1000 Gy, which comprises the value of $\sim 770 \pm 150$ Gy reported in Tsukamoto et al., 2018. The level of saturation (I_0) is 2-3 times lower for the natural DRCs than for the laboratory ones.

The laboratory DRCs for Ti centres reach saturation at the level 4-5 times higher than the natural DRCs. The D_0 values obtained from the fitting were 4508 ± 544 , 3135 ± 238 , 3921 ± 152 Gy for sample 06, and 4352 ± 386 , 4003 ± 357 , 5053 ± 470 Gy for sample 12, option A, B, D, respectively (**Table 2**). These values were considerably larger than the ones obtained for the natural DRCs, and, although slightly higher, are not far from the value 3200 ± 200 Gy given by Tsukamoto et al. (2018) for the measurements without preheat, and they fall within the range from 2700 to 4700 Gy reported in Rink et al., 2007.

For the Al-h centre, the level of saturation of the laboratory DRCs is 2-3 times higher than for the natural curve. D_0 values obtained for laboratory DRCs were 4922 ± 547 Gy for sample 06, and 3379 ± 622 Gy for sample 12 (**Table 2**), which also fall within the range reported by Rink et al. (2007), spanning from 3000 to more than 6000 Gy. The value obtained for sample 12 agrees within the uncertainty with the one given by Tsukamoto et al. (2018) for the measurements without preheat, which was reported as 2600 ± 400 Gy.

3.3 Thermal stability

When dating procedures are carried out laboratory signals are generated with a much higher dose rate and measured immediately after irradiation, thus their thermal decay can be neglected. Contrastingly, during natural irradiation the accumulation of trapped charge and its constant decay are happening simultaneously and are competing processes, causing the shape of the “ideal natural DRC” (the natural DRC which would only be the result of the natural irradiation without any thermal decay) to be constantly modified and flattened. This can be further explained using the mathematical description provided by Christodoulides et al.

(1971), which leads to the conclusion that both the number of filled traps and the saturation dose will be larger for higher dose rates, resulting in laboratory D_0 values being higher than natural D_0 values.

Moreover, by analysing a quartz sample extracted from loess in Nebraska, Benzid & Timar Gabor (2020) presented a dose dependence of the thermal stability of Al and Ti defects and suggested this can explain the differences between the saturation level of the natural and laboratory DRCs observed by Tsukamoto et al. (2018). When we additionally consider such a dose-dependency of the decay rates, the thermal decay becomes even more significant at higher doses, leading to a further divergence of the natural and laboratory DRCs.

In order to test this effect on quartz from Luochuan four samples were selected for pulse annealing ESR experiments: D881 01c – a natural Holocene sample with expected dose 3 ± 0.3 Gy, D881 11 – natural sample with expected dose 900 ± 90 Gy (L3 bottom), and D881 06 – natural sample with expected dose 384 ± 38 Gy (S1 bottom) additionally irradiated with 500 Gy and 1000 Gy (total doses 884 ± 90 Gy and 1384 ± 141 Gy, respectively). The total absorbed dose for the sample D881 06 irradiated with 500 Gy, and the natural sample D881 11 was therefore the same. Thermal stability of the samples was investigated in temperature range 295-895 K, with each heating step lasting for 10 min. The decay of ESR intensity with temperature was fitted using second order kinetics equation derived by Benzid & Timar Gabor (2020):

$$N_H^{2nd} = (N_D - N_0) \left(1 + \frac{sk_B}{QE} \left(T^2 e^{-\left(\frac{E}{k_B T}\right)} - T_0^2 e^{-\left(\frac{E}{k_B T_0}\right)} \right) \right)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

where: $(N_D - N_0)$ – initial effective concentration in respect of the accumulated gamma dose (N_0 being the final concentration, fixed as 0), s – frequency factor (s^{-1}), k_B – Boltzmann constant ($8.615 \cdot 10^{-5}$ eV/K), Q – heating rate ($Q = dT/dt$ (see Section 2.3)), E – activation energy (eV), T_0 – initial temperature (295 K).

The results of the pulse annealing experiment for Al-h and Ti centres are shown in **Fig. 3**. It can be observed that the signals of the samples which received a higher dose of radiation drop faster than the low dose signals. While the intensity of the signals for the highest dose starts to decay around 450 K, the signal intensity for the lowest dose remains constant up to about 500 K. Two samples with the similar total dose (D881 11 and D881 06 irradiated with 500 Gy) exhibit a very similar decay. As such, the data shows an apparent dose-dependent thermal instability of the Al-h and Ti signals.

To our knowledge, besides Benzid & Timar Gabor (2020), only two other studies present the results of ESR annealing experiments conducted on quartz irradiated with different doses. The earliest example of was reported by Rink et al. (2007). They compared the results of isochronal annealing for the natural and additionally irradiated (with 2.2 kGy) sample. Additionally, for Al centres Rink et al. (2007) added a plot for the natural sample after 170 h exposure using the solar simulator. It is visible from the data, especially after normalizing the intensities that the Al and Ti signals of the additionally irradiated sample exhibit a faster decay than of the natural one, and the signals of the sample exposed to light are more stable than the natural ones. Rink et al. concluded that the artificially induced signal might be somewhat less stable than the natural signal, but did not provide any further analysis of the matter. Most recently, at the LED 2021 conference, Wen et al. showed the results of ESR pulse annealing experiment on quartz samples from European Alps, which also seem to show the apparent dose-dependent thermal stability of the ESR signals. Their data showed that the Al and Ti signals in samples irradiated with 6180 Gy regenerative dose exhibited a decay at lower temperatures than the natural signals.

In the light of the experimental data obtained, to visualize the effect of thermal instability on the shape of DRC we simulated several DRCs resulting from a thermal decay of selected points on the original DRC curve, first with a constant decay rate (**Fig. S3**), then with decay rates increasing with dose (**Fig. 4a**). To start with, a DRC was simulated using single saturating exponential function with parameters $I_0 = 1$, $D_0 = 1500$ Gy, $D_E = 40$ Gy. Then, six datapoints on the curve were selected, corresponding with the doses 1000, 2000, 3000, 5000, 7000, 10000 Gy, for which the decay curves were plotted, following the first-order kinetics equation:

$$I = I_0 e^{(-At)} \quad (7)$$

In the first scenario, one decay rate $A = 0.05$ was chosen (**Fig. S3**), while in the second scenario the decay rates were set as 0.05, 0.07, 0.08, 0.09, 0.1, 0.11, increasing with the irradiation dose (**Fig. 4a**). New intensities obtained for arbitrary values of decay time t , $2.5t$, $5t$, $7.5t$ were plotted against the corresponding dose, and the new DRCs were fitted with single saturating exponential functions. Obviously, the saturation intensity of the DRCs gradually decreased with longer decay times. We observed that using a constant decay rate resulted in new DRCs with the same saturation characteristic (D_0 value) as the original curve (**Fig. S3**). However, using the increasing values of the decay rates resulted in D_0 values gradually decreasing with decay time, from the original value of 1500 Gy, to 1300 ± 18 , 1070

± 24 , 716 ± 15 , and 453 ± 9 Gy, for t , $2.5t$, $5t$, and $7.5t$, respectively (**Fig. 4a**). Additionally, for longer decay times a decrease of intensity below the saturation level could be observed for high doses, and these datapoints were consequently left out from the DRC fitting. These simulations show that assuming a dose-dependent thermal instability, where the signal is less thermally stable for higher doses, results in a decrease of D_0 value if a thermal treatment is applied.

To further investigate this hypothesis, we used the data presented by Tsukamoto et al. (2018) for Luochuan quartz samples. The DRCs for Al-h centre shown in Fig. 4a therein were obtained after the application of different preheat temperatures: no preheat, 150, 180, 210, 240°C, with preheat time of 4 min, and fitted with a single saturating exponential. Tsukamoto et al. observed a decrease of D_0 values with increasing preheat temperature, from $D_0 = 2600 \pm 400$ Gy for the curve with no preheat, to 2100 ± 400 , 1700 ± 300 , 1500 ± 300 , and 1200 ± 300 Gy for 150, 180, 210, and 240°C, respectively. Similar decrease in D_0 values was also observed for the Ti centres (Fig. 4b therein). As mentioned earlier, Tsukamoto et al., 2018 also observed that the higher preheat temperatures bring the laboratory DRC closer to the natural one, although the D_0 values for these preheated curves were still much larger than those obtained for the natural DRC.

We plotted their data for Al-h (**Fig. 4b**), and selected five doses: 100, 200, 500, 1000, 2000, 5000 Gy, marking five points on each of the four DRCs obtained by preheating. For these 20 points we then calculated the decay rates from the equation:

$$A_{D_i T_j} = \ln \frac{I_{D_i T_j}}{I_{0D_i T_j}} t \quad (8)$$

where $A_{D_i T_j}$ – decay rate for a given dose D_i and preheat temperature T_j , $I_{D_i T_j}$ – signal intensity for a given dose and preheat temperature, $I_{0D_i T_j}$ – original signal intensity for a given dose D_i and temperature T_j , t – preheat time (4 min). The calculated decay rates values, presented in **Table 3**, show a clear trend of increase with the irradiation dose, visualised by the decay curves plotted for each point in **Fig 4b**. The decrease in D_0 values observed by Tsukamoto et al. can therefore be explained by a dose-dependent thermal instability.

While Tsukamoto et al. (2018) suggested that the differences between the natural and laboratory DRCs are the result of thermal instability, here we have clearly shown that only by assuming this instability to be dose dependent both the differences between the natural and laboratory DRCs and the change in the D_0 values with preheat can be explained.

It should be noted, that while the aforementioned theoretical description provided by Christodoulides et al. (1971), shows that both the saturation level and the saturation dose

depend of dose rate and temperature (resulting in laboratory D_0 values being higher than natural D_0 values), it does not take into account the potential effects of applied dose of radiation. This description was provided for a constant number of available traps, but just a few years later Durrani et al. (1977) postulated based on TL experiments, that large doses cause structural changes in the material, which leads to creation of additional traps, thus making this assumption invalid. Recently, Townsend et al. (2021) published an in-depth analysis of evidence of defect clustering reported by many authors, which clearly shows that the traditional concept of charge transfer between traps via the conduction band (the delocalized model) is far too idealised. Later models introduced the concept of a close association of the trap and the recombination centre (localized recombination). It is beyond the scope of our paper to provide the mathematical description of the trapping and recombination processes by introducing the observed dose-dependency of the decay rates into the equation, but it is clear that more studies, both experimental and theoretical, are necessary for more appropriate models to be developed.

4. Conclusions

The natural and laboratory ESR dose response curves of Al and Ti centres from Luochuan show a clear divergence above ~ 1000 Gy, with much lower D_0 values and saturation levels observed for the natural DRCs. These results are in agreement with the previous study by Tsukamoto et al. (2018). Significant residual signals corresponding to several tens to hundreds of Gy were found to be present in both Al and Ti centres and were taken into account before laboratory DRC construction. The ESR pulse annealing experiments performed on samples irradiated with different doses show that thermal stability of Al and Ti is dependent on the irradiation dose, causing the signals from higher doses to decay faster with increasing temperature. The earlier saturation of the natural DRC, being a result of reaching the equilibrium between filling of the traps and emptying them due to thermal decay (rather than filling all the available traps, as in the case of laboratory irradiation), is therefore additionally affected for higher doses, due to the increased thermal instability. Based on our findings, we attribute the change in D_0 with preheat reported in Tsukamoto et al., 2018, as well as the difference between laboratory and natural DRCs, to an apparent dose-dependent thermal instability of the signals. It is our hope that these results will provoke more research in this topic, as they pose a serious concern for ESR dating.

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Fig 1. Mass normalized amplitudes of young natural samples from Luochuan (D881 and A881), Jingbian (D381) and modern samples from Zhou he zhen bei and Shi mao (D), for Al-h centre (a), and Ti centres, option A, B, D (signals for Jingbian and modern samples were below the detection limit) (b). Dashed bands indicate the amplitudes of the signals in the sample with an expected dose of 960 Gy (D881 12). Average amplitudes calculated from young Luochuan samples were 1.136 ± 0.006 for Al-h, and 0.036 ± 0.002 , 0.038 ± 0.002 , 0.027 ± 0.002 for Ti centres, for option A, B, and D respectively.

Fig 2. Al-h (a), and Ti option A (b), B (c), D (d) mass normalized amplitudes of samples from Luochuan (D881), natural and laboratory irradiated (D881 06 and 12), corrected for the residual signal. Total dose is the sum of the expected and laboratory dose (in the case of natural samples total dose is the same as the expected dose). The inset shows the same data but plotted against the laboratory given dose. D_E values for Al-h obtained from fitting were 1061 ± 103 Gy for sample D881 06 and 925 ± 181 Gy for sample D881 12. D_E values obtained for Ti from fitting for sample D881 06 were 431 ± 75 Gy, 489 ± 53 Gy, 451 ± 25 Gy for options A, B, D respectively; and for sample D881 12 the values were 1421 ± 109 Gy, 1244 ± 102 Gy, 1426 ± 106 Gy, for option A, B, D, respectively. The dose response curves (DRCs) were fitted with a single saturated exponential function without any weighting using Origin software.

Fig. 3 ESR intensity of Al-h (a), and Ti option A (b), B (c), D (d) as a function of annealing temperature, fitted with the second order kinetics function (equation 2). Empty symbols designate the datapoints excluded from the fitting. Fitting was done without any weighting using Origin software.

Fig. 4 (a) Simulated DRCs resulting from a thermal decay of selected points on the original curve, with decay rates increasing with the dose and for arbitrary values of decay time t , $2.5t$, $5t$, $7.5t$. Several datapoints were excluded from the fit: the last point for t , two last points for $2.5t$ and $5t$, and three last points for $7.5t$. (b) Data redrawn from Tsukamoto et al., 2018 (Fig. 4a therein), using the reported values of D_0 , I_0 values estimated from the graph, and $D_E = 0$. Decay curves were plotted for each marked datapoint and the preheat time of 4 min.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

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Table 1. Sample and site information. The expected dose is the measured equivalent dose using SAR OSL (A881 samples this work, D samples Buylaert et al. (2011) and D381 samples Stevens et al., (2018)). Uncertainties are standard errors. For D881 samples (those denoted with *) the dose is estimated by multiplying the expected age of the sample based on Ding et al., 2002 by the average dose rate of 3 Gy/ka (Chapot et al., 2012), with 10% uncertainty. Number of aliquots was 25, 19, 21 and 6, for samples A881 01, 25, 34 and D881 02, respectively.

Sample	Site	Unit	Fraction	Expected dose (Gy)	± (Gy)
A881	Luochuan (Xiaheimu)	plough layer		1.54	0.05
		L1	63-90	54.5	2.5
		L1		42.3	1.9
D881	Luochuan (Potou)	S0		3*	0.3
		L1		30	2
		S1 bottom		384*	38
		L2 middle		480*	48
		L2 bottom		540*	54
		S2 middle		660*	66
		L3 bottom	63-90	900*	90
		S3 middle		960*	96
		L4 top		1020*	102
		S5		1596*	160
		L17		4002*	400
		L25		5303*	530
30		Tertiary-Quaternary boundary	7500*	750	
D381	Jingbian	S0	90-180	7.4	0.4
		L1		39.2	1.6
D	Zhou he zhen bei	top few cm	63-90	0.65	0.1
	Shi mao	of loess section		0.13	0.02

Table 2 Equivalent doses and D_0 values obtained from natural and laboratory DRCs.

DRC	Al-h		Ti A		Ti B		Ti D	
	D_E (Gy)	D_0 (Gy)						
Lab 06	1061 ± 103	4922 ± 547	483 ± 75	4508 ± 544	489 ± 53	3135 ± 238	451 ± 25	3921 ± 152
Lab 12	925 ± 181	3379 ± 622	1421 ± 109	4352 ± 386	1244 ± 10	4003 ± 357	1426 ± 106	5053 ± 470
Natural		500-1000		830 ± 350		883 ± 451		665 ± 336

Table 3 Decay rate values calculated based on the data presented in Tsukamoto et al., 2018, Fig.4a.

Dose (Gy)	Temperature (°C)			
	150	180	210	240
200	0.00010	0.00010	0.00091	0.00203
500	0.00016	0.00016	0.00096	0.00212
1000	0.00024	0.00026	0.00103	0.00226
2000	0.00039	0.00043	0.00114	0.00249
5000	0.00070	0.00075	0.00133	0.00280